

JURISPRUDENCE

EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS INDIVIDUAL MEASURES EXECUTION. CATALYZING JUDICIAL REFORMS IN ALBANIA

Iva Tërova (Pendavinji)

Phd., Candidate,

Fan.S.Noli University, Korça, Albania

Nadia Rusi

Assoc. Prof. Dr.,

University of Tirana, Tirana, Albania

Abstract

This article aims to analyze the individual measures in the context of executing the European Court of Human Rights judgments, with particular emphasis on those that have shown the potential to promote legal reforms, as a result of the identification of structural problems in national legislation and practice. The article illustrates that the transformative impact of the ECtHR jurisprudence is not limited to decisions that suggest general measures, but also extends to those cases where individual measures are determined.

Within this analysis, only those decisions of the Court that are considered illustrative and significant for the purposes of the study will be brought to attention, especially those that clearly reflect an impact in the national legal order by identifying and addressing structural problems. The selection of these decisions seeks to reflect the transformative role, without claiming an exhaustive treatment of all the relevant jurisprudence.

The article focuses on the positive obligations of Albanian state and national implementation mechanisms assessing the extent to which the compliance with ECtHR's judgments has contributed to the legislative amendments. It concludes that effective execution triggers broader judicial reform.

Keywords: European Court of Human Rights; European Court of Human Rights; jurisprudence; individual measures; legal reforms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Individual measures are specific legal remedies defined in the operative part of European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) judgment. Pursuant to Article 46 of the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR), their purpose is to require the respondent States to take measures to improve the legal position of applicants, by placing them, as far as possible, in the position they would have been in had the violation not occurred. Contracting States, in accordance with the principle of subsidiarity, enjoy autonomy to choose the measures to implement the decisions of the ECHR, while retaining the primary responsibility of the Contracting States to guarantee respect for the rights and freedoms protected by the Convention. (Papamichalopoulos and Others v. Greece (Article 50), § 34) This obligation is also linked to the implementation of Article 1 of the ECHR, which imposes on States the positive obligation to ensure respect for the fundamental rights and freedoms set out in the Convention. Despite the fact that the decisions of the ECtHR are mainly declaratory, in certain cases the Court may instruct states on the individual/general measures that must be taken to eliminate the violations found. (Suso Musa v. Malta, § 120)

This is due to the nature of the violation is such that the determination of the individual measure becomes necessary for the execution of the decision. Hence, they represent a shift from the traditional declaratory approach of the Court's judgments, by directly orienting the execution process and by limiting the discretion of the states in the choice of reparative measures. (Janhn, 2024) As the author Jahn notes, the ordering of individual measures constitutes a

mechanism through which the Court clearly address the execution of the decision at the national level, limiting the margin of discretion that the Convention recognizes for the domestic authorities. (Janhn, 2024, p.2)

Over time, the Court's case-law has gradually penetrated national legal orders, while States parties to the Convention have generally shown themselves willing to accept its reparative powers. (Stone Sweet, 2012, p.53) This development has helped limit arbitrariness and inefficiency in domestic political and judicial processes, while simultaneously strengthening the position of the individual vis-à-vis the state. (Hefler, 2008)

Individual measures often highlight the existence of structural problems within the State Parties. Beyond providing redress to the applicant, they may indicate the necessity for broader systemic reforms. This article therefore analyses selected ECtHR judgments against Albania that have surfaced such deficiencies, showing that the state responded not only through the payment of just satisfaction but also by adopting general measures. Illustrative cases concerning various Convention violations are examined to demonstrate the corresponding the legal changes in Albanian domestic law.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

The article adopts a qualitative, doctrinal legal methodology, based on the analyses of legal norms and judicial reasoning. It examines the legal framework governing the execution of ECtHR judgments, referencing to article 46 of ECHR, and analysis selected judgments of the court concerning Albania and other

states. It draws on the ECtHR's HUDOC database, to select the cases based on their significance in illustrating the application of the individual measures and their impact on Albanian legal reforms. In this context, the article relies on relevant academic literature and official documents as well.

3. THE STATUS OF ECHR AND ECtHR JURISPRUDENCE IN ALBANIAN LEGAL ORDER

According to Article 116 of the Constitution of Albania, the Convention as a ratified international agreement holds a supra-legal position in the hierarchy of normative acts, meaning that it is positioned below the Constitution but above ordinary laws. (Parliamentary Assembly, 1998) This hierarchy ensures that if a national law conflicts with the provisions of the Convention, it is considered unconstitutional, as well as anti-conventional. Furthermore, Article 122(2) further asserts the primacy over domestic laws that are incompatible with it. This implies that Albania has a duty to respect its international commitments, giving the European Convention on Human Rights a fundamental importance in the development of the legal system and the guarantee of human rights in the country. Furthermore, Article 5 of the Constitution of Albania expressly provides that the Republic of Albania shall implement the international law that is binding on it. Regarding restrictions on rights and freedoms, Article 17 states that any restrictions must be imposed by law, based on the public interest or the protection of the rights of others. It is important to emphasize that these restrictions must be proportionate to the situation and may not violate the essence of the rights provided for in the Constitution, nor may they exceed the limitations set out in the European Convention on Human Rights.

The status of ECHR and the binding force of the ECtHR jurisprudence has also been consistently affirmed in the case law by the Albanian Constitutional Court and Supreme Court jurisprudence.

In decision no. 22 dated 9 March 2010, the Constitutional Court held that: "...The judgments of the ECHR are binding on the member states of the Council of Europe, that are parties to the Convention, in accordance with the the commitments arising from Article 46/1 thereof"

Subsequently, in decision no. 20, dated 01 June 2011, the Constitutional Court reaffirmed that the ECtHR has exclusive jurisdiction to interpret the Convention and that its judgments are directly applicable in the domestic legal order, pursuant to Articles 122 and 17/2 of the Constitution, 19 and 46 of the Convention. The court reiterated that in the absence of legislative harmonization with the ECHR, judges at all levels are obliged to directly implement the decisions of the ECHR.

A similar position was adopted by the Criminal Chamber of the Supreme Court, in Decision No. 74 dated 7.3.2012, the Criminal Chamber of the Supreme Court, among other things, assessed that the Supreme Court takes into account the hierarchy of legal norms and judicial decisions, thus giving the decisions of the

European Court of Human Rights an important upper place, considering them in this regard, the peak of the pyramid"

This approach was further confirmed in decision no.00-2021-1317, dated 22.7.2021 of Supreme Court of Albania. Accordingly, due to the constitutional status of the ECHR, ordinary courts cannot avoid applying national laws when they consider that they are in conflict with the Convention. (Supreme Court of Albania, 2021, §47)

The Chamber reiterated that the refusal of the courts to directly apply the ECHR and the practice of the ECtHR on the grounds of the absence or contradiction of domestic law and pending legislative or constitutional interventions, is contrary to Article 46 of the ECHR and the obligation to take prompt and effective measures to restore the previous situation. (Supreme Court of Albania, 2021, §148) Thus, the direct implementation of ECHR decisions is essential even in conditions of legislative omission or inconsistencies with domestic law. (Supreme Court of Albania, 2021, §149)

4. INDIVIDUAL MEASURES AND THE ABILITY TO TRIGGER LEGAL REFORMS

Individual measures play an important role in the process of implementing ECtHR judgments, in compliance with Article 46 of the ECHR, not only by addressing specific violations, but also by signaling structural problems that may arise in the legislation or judicial practice of a given State. According to Article 46, in the event of the identification of one or more violations of the provisions of the ECHR, the Court imposes on the State a legal obligation to put an end to the violation and to place the applicant in the position he would have been in if the violation had not been committed (Papamichalopoulos and Others v. Greece (Article 50), 1995, § 34). However, the Contracting State concerned is not only under an obligation to pay the applicant just satisfaction under Article 41 of the ECHR, as an individual measure of a pecuniary nature, but also to take individual non-pecuniary and, if appropriate, general measures in its domestic legal order to put an end to the violation found by the Court and to redress its effects (Ilgar Mammadov v. Azerbaijan [GC], 2019, § 147).

The State party to the case is, in principle, free to choose the means by which it will implement a judgment in which the Court has found a violation. This discretion as to the manner of execution of a judgment reflects the freedom of choice attached to the primary obligation of the Contracting States under the Convention to secure the rights and freedoms guaranteed (Papamichalopoulos and Others v. Greece (Article 50), 1995, § 34). This discretion also serves to assess the ability of national legal systems to translate the Court's decisions into tangible results, as will be evident in the jurisprudence against Albania.

Referring to the jurisprudence against Albania, in addition to determining just compensation under Article 41 of the Convention, i.e. individual measures of a material nature, the Court has also recommended individual measures of a non-material nature, within the meaning of Article 46, such as: In the case of

Ramadhi and Others v. Albania, the Court recommended the return of land as a compulsory measure. (Ramadhi and Others v. Albania, 2007, § 102)

In the case of Gjonbocari v. Albania, structural problems were found in the non-enforcement of final decisions of domestic courts and administrative decisions on the restitution or compensation of property nationalized during the communist regime. This led to a violation of Article 6§1 and Article 1 of Protocol No. 1, as well as the lack of an effective remedy (violation of Article 13 in conjunction with Article 6§1). The Court emphasized that the government must ensure, by appropriate means and promptly, the enforcement of the final decision of the domestic courts. In this context, as an individual non-pecuniary measure, the authorities were requested to provide information on the implementation of the procedures for the enforcement of a Supreme Court's decision. (Gjonbocari and Others v. Albania, 2007)

In the case of Jella and Others v. Albania, (Jella and Others v. Albania, 2024) the Court considered the most appropriate form of reparation to be the demarcation of the land and the registration of the title to the land of the applicants. This was considered a measure which placed the applicants in the situation in which they would have been if the violation had not occurred. If the Government were unable to secure such registration, either in whole or in part, the applicants should receive adequate compensation. (Jella and Others v. Albania, 2024, §32)

In the following cases, the ECHR determined just satisfaction in line with Article 41 of the ECHR or individual measures of a non-pecuniary nature based on Article 46. As will be evident, regardless of these measures, the Albanian State showed its willingness and initiative to take general measures with the aim of ending the repetition of the violation of rights but also of solving structural problems.

In *Biba v. Albania*, the matter concerned a student who suffered a 90% loss of vision after being struck in the eye by a projectile that was fired from a rubber catapult by another student during school hours. (*Biba v. Albania*, 2024)

The Court reaffirmed its dynamic understanding of "private and family life," interpreting the concept to include both physical and psychological integrity. It held that the injury suffered had a serious and lasting impact on the child's well-being, thus bringing the incident within the protective scope of Article 8. Notably, the Court treated school safety as an emerging area that necessitates proactive State intervention. Through an evolutive interpretation, it integrated institutional accountability in education into the framework of Convention rights (*Biba v. Albania*, 2024, §§41–43).

Emphasizing children's vulnerability and the institutional responsibilities of schools, the Court held that Article 8 requires not only non-interference but also the active enforcement of safety standards. Both public and private educational institutions are obliged to maintain discipline and prevent violence throughout the school day. Drawing on its earlier jurisprudence, the Court emphasized that States cannot delegate responsibility to private actors. Effective supervision

and legal safeguards are essential to fulfilling Article 8 obligations, particularly in cases involving peer-on-peer violence and the presence of dangerous objects (*Biba v. Albania*, 2024, §§ 59–60, 66–68, 71–73, 77).

Upon reviewing the Albanian legal and institutional framework, especially Section 66 of Law No. 7952 and the supervisory role of the Ministry of Education, the Court acknowledged the existence of some preventive mechanisms. However, it found that enforcement was inadequate. The failure to ensure preventive supervision and effective legal remedies constituted a breach of Albania's positive obligations under Article 8. The Court concluded that States must implement practical and effective measures, not merely theoretical frameworks, to protect children from foreseeable risks within educational settings.

In response to the Court's judgment, the Albanian Government submitted a Revised Action Plan on 7 February 2025 to the Committee of Ministers (1521st meeting, March 2025), (Albania, 2025) outlining systemic reforms to implement the ruling. Among the key measures was the national rollout of a "School Safety Package" in 2024, which deployed 240 security officers to schools across the country to address bullying, violence, and cyberbullying. Complementary initiatives included the "Smart City" project, aimed at improving public and school safety through upgraded surveillance infrastructure. Capacity-building efforts were also enhanced through OSCE-led training sessions on conflict de-escalation. Furthermore, Albania advanced its cooperation with the Council of Europe via the "Strengthening Democratic Citizenship Education" project, which promotes human rights and democratic values in school curricula.

The case of *Xheraj v. Albania* represents a significant milestone in the domestic enforcement of ECtHR judgments within Albania. The applicant contended that the Supreme Court undermined legal certainty by permitting a prosecutor to challenge a final acquittal beyond the established legal deadline. The ECtHR determined that there was a breach of Article 6(1), highlighting the importance of the finality of judicial decisions and safeguarding individual legal expectations (*Xheraj v. Albania*, 2008). Importantly, the Court invoked Article 41 to assert that reopening proceedings constituted an effective remedy, even in the absence of a specific legal provision in Albanian law permitting such actions. This ruling implicitly utilized evolutive interpretation: although the Convention does not prescribe particular domestic procedures for the execution of ECtHR judgments, the Court's rationale encouraged the amendment of national law to guarantee the practical and effective implementation of Strasbourg decisions. The consequences of this ruling are noteworthy. The Constitutional Court mandated the Supreme Court to reopen the case (Constitutional Court of Albania, 2010), resulting in the annulment of the applicant's conviction and the expungement of his criminal record (Supreme Court of Albania, 2012). Following this, Albania revised Article 450(d) of its Criminal Procedure Code (Law No. 7905/1995) (Assembly of Albanian Republic, 1995) to explicitly permit the reopening of proceedings in instances of ECtHR

violations. This legislative change exemplifies how evolutive interpretation can drive systemic legal reforms to ensure that domestic law aligns with the evolving obligations of human rights.

In *Dauti v. Albania*, the ECtHR held that the lack of judicial review over decisions by the Appeals Commission violated the applicant's right to a fair trial under Article 6 (*Dauti v. Albania*, 2009). Albanian courts had previously deemed these decisions final and unchallengeable. The Court's ruling required not merely the correction of an individual violation but the evolution of national legislation to ensure access to justice. This judgment prompted the Albanian legislature to amend Law No. 7703 ("On Social Insurance") through Law No. 10 447 of 14 July 2011 (Assembly of Albanian Republic, 2011), introducing judicial oversight over such decisions. However, concerns persisted about the practical implementation of the reform. In 2021, the Supreme Court raised questions regarding its authority to directly apply international law and the legal significance of the enforcement decisions made by the Committee of Ministers. In Decision No. 55/2021, the Constitutional Court opted not to offer a binding interpretation, choosing instead to defer the matter to the Supreme Court. (Constitutional Court of Albania, 2021). The Supreme Court later determined that the revised law continued to fall short of meeting the criteria outlined in Article 6. It declared the conflicting provisions inoperable and reaffirmed the duty of national courts to apply the ECHR directly, even in the face of contradictory domestic law (Supreme Court of Albania, 2021). The case reflects the Court's evolutive approach to access to justice, expanding the reach of procedural protections. It further affirms the primacy of ECtHR jurisprudence in directing national legal reform, thereby reinforcing the living character of the Convention.

In *Luli and Others v. Albania*, the European Court of Human Rights found a violation of Article 6 § 1 on account of the excessive length of judicial proceedings, stressing that undue delays undermine the fairness of a trial irrespective of its complexity. (*Luli and Others v. Albania*, 2014, §92). The Court observed that repeated referrals for re-examination by administrative bodies exposed systemic deficiencies within Albania's legal framework. Moreover, consistent with its earlier case law against Albania, the Court held that no effective domestic remedy existed for complaints concerning the length of proceedings, underscoring a structural flaw in the national legal system. According to Article 6, States are required to organize their judicial systems so that competent authorities can resolve cases within a reasonable timeframe. This involves taking procedural steps like consolidating cases, halting unnecessary actions, or dismissing repetitive claims to comply with the Convention's time constraints. In its analysis under Article 46, the Court went beyond individual redress and called for structural reforms, urging Albania to introduce an effective remedy for excessive judicial delays (*Luli and Others v. Albania*, 2014, §§ 116–118). The judgment exemplifies the Court's reliance on evolutive interpretation, treating the Convention as a "living instrument" that necessitates the adaptation of

domestic law to contemporary standards of justice. Its expansive reading of "reasonable time" under article 6 reflects a dynamic understanding of procedural fairness, addressing systematic dysfunction instead of isolated delays.

Following the judgment, Albania enacted Law No. 38/2017, amending Title III of the Civil Procedure Code (CPC) by adding Chapter X on "Examination of Requests Concerning Violations of the Reasonable Timeframe, Acceleration of Procedures, and Compensation for Damages" (covering Articles 399/1 to 399/12) (Assembly of Albanian Republic, 1991). These provisions sought to mitigate procedural delays by establishing clear timelines for various stages of the judicial process, thereby enhancing efficiency and alleviating court backlogs. This legislative response demonstrates the practical impact of evolutive interpretation, whereby the ECtHR's ruling catalyzed the alignment of Albania's domestic legal system with contemporary human rights obligations and strengthened the effectiveness of the Convention in practice.

The case of *Bajrami v. Albania* concerned the failure of the Albanian authorities to fulfil their positive obligation to guarantee the applicant's right to family life, specifically reunification with his daughter, in breach of Article 8 of the Convention.

The Court found that, following the separation, the applicant was almost completely deprived of contact with his child and that, despite his requests and warnings of abduction of the child by his ex-wife, the authorities failed to prevent the daughter from leaving the country without his consent, nor to subsequently enforce the court decision granting him custody.

In this situation, the Court highlighted the fact that the legal system did not provide for any effective legal means to prevent or punish child abduction, nor an alternative to enable family reunification, (*Bajrami v. Albania*, 2006 § 67) and concluded that the authorities' efforts were neither sufficient nor effective to fulfil this positive obligation, leading to a violation of Article 8 of the Convention. (*Bajrami v. Albania*, 2006 §§ 68–69)

In response to the findings and problems in the legal framework regarding the protection of children, and in particular protection from international abductions, the Albanian state ratified the Hague Convention "On the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction".(1980) The purposes of this Convention are: a. to secure the prompt return of children wrongfully removed or retained in a Contracting State; and b. to ensure that rights of custody and contact under the law of a Contracting State are effectively respected in other Contracting States.(Article 1)

As part of the measures taken to implement the ECHR decision, Law No. 18/2017 'On the Rights and Protection of the Child' was adopted. (2017) This law transposed the UNCRC convention into the domestic legal system and defined the institutional mechanisms responsible for protecting children's rights. (Article 34)

Another reform regarding the execution of decisions was the adoption of Law No. 26/2019 "On the private bailiff service", adopted on 8.5.2019, which

repealed Law No. 10 031, dated 11.12.2008, "On the private bailiff service", as amended. (Assembly of Albanian Republic, 2019) According to Article 53, point 3, in cases of execution of executive titles that have as their object the visitation and custody of the child, the private judicial enforcement officer has the obligation to notify the child protection unit at the structure responsible for social services in the municipality, as well as to request the assistance of a psychologist.

As an additional preventive measure, Albania has introduced a biometric passport system for children, increasing the security of travel documents. (Albania, 2018, §§19-20)

After examining the action report provided by the government indicating the measures taken to implement the Bajrami v. Albania judgment, the Committee of Ministers decided to close its examination. (Committee of Ministers, 2018)

5. CONCLUSION

The article highlighted that individual measures imposed by the European Court of Human Rights have played an important role in advancing legal reforms within the Albanian legal system. In addition to addressing individual cases, these measures have often highlighted structural deficiencies in domestic legislation and judicial practices, prompting the state to respond with normative and institutional changes. In this context, they constitute a fundamental aspect of the process of executing decisions by making rights practical and not illusory. They are also a determining factor in transforming Strasbourg decisions into tangible results within the national legal framework.

References

1. Albania. (2018, March 27). Action report (27/03/2018) – Communication from Albania concerning the case of Bajrami v. Albania (Application No. 35853/04), 1318th meeting (June 2018) (DH). HUDOC-EXEC. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from [https://hudoc.exec.coe.int/?i=DH-DD\(2018\)369E](https://hudoc.exec.coe.int/?i=DH-DD(2018)369E)
2. Albania. (2025, February 7). Revised Action Plan (07/02/2025) - Communication from Albania concerning the case of Biba v. Albania (Application No. 24228/18), 1521st meeting (March 2025) (DH). HUDOC-EXEC. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from [https://hudoc.exec.coe.int/eng/?i=DH-DD\(2025\)147revE](https://hudoc.exec.coe.int/eng/?i=DH-DD(2025)147revE)
3. Assembly of Albanian Republic. (1991, April 29). Law No.7491 "Code of the Civil Procedure of the Republic of Albania." EURALIUS. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://euralius.eu/index.php/en/library/albanian-legislation?task=download.send&id=172∓catid=11∓m=0>
4. Assembly of Albanian Republic. (1995, March 21). Law No.7905 "CRIMINAL PROCEDURE CODE OF THE REPUBLIC OF ALBANIA". EURALIUS. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://euralius.eu/index.php/en/library/albanian-legislation?task=download.send&id=172∓catid=11∓m=0>
5. Assembly of Albanian Republic. (2011, July 14). Law No.10447 "On some additional provisions on the law 7703/1993 "On social security".
6. Assembly of Albanian Republic. (2017, February 23). Law No. 18/2017 on the Rights and Protection of the Child.
7. Assembly of Albanian Republic. (2019, May 8). Law No. 26/2019 "On the Private Bailiff Service." Qendra e Botimeve Zyrtare. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://qbz.gov.al/eli/ligj/2019/05/08/26/33ad5732-eb8b-443f-910f-ef8bdc0eb71d>
8. Bajrami v. Albania. (2006, December 12). European Court of Human Rights. HUDOC – European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 35853/04. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-78425>
9. Biba v. Albania. (2024, May 7). European Court of Human Right, Application no. 24228/18. HUDOC - European Court of Human Rights. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng/?i=001-233411>
10. Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe. (2018, May 2). Resolution CM/ResDH(2018)173 – Execution of the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights: Bajrami v. Albania, 1315th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies. HUDOC-EXEC. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.exec.coe.int/?i=001-183106>
11. Constitutional Court of Albania. (2010, March 9). Decision no. 22. Gjykata Kushtetuese. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <http://gjk.gov.al>
12. Constitutional Court of Albania. (2010, May 5). Decision no. 22. Gjykata Kushtetuese. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <http://gjk.gov.al>
13. Constitutional Court of Albania. (2011, June 1). Decision no. 20. Gjykata Kushtetuese. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <http://gjk.gov.al>
14. Constitutional Court of Albania. (2021, March 31). Decision no. 55. Gjykata Kushtetuese. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://www.gjk.gov.al/>
15. Council of Europe. (1950, November 4). European Convention on Human Rights. ECHR. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/d/echr/Convention_ENG
16. Dauti v. Albania. (2009, February 3). European Court of Human Rights,. HUDOC - European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 19206/05. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng/?i=001-91103>
17. Gjonbocari and Others v. Albania. (2007, October 23). European Court of Human Rights. HUDOC – European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 10508/02. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-82863>
18. Hague Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction. (1980, October 25). Ratified by Albania, Law no. 9446, 24 November 2005.
19. Helfer, L. R. (2008). Redesigning the European Court of Human Rights: Embeddedness as a deep structural principle of the European human rights regime. *European Journal of International Law*, 19(1), 125–159. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chn004>

20. Ilgar Mammadov v. Azerbaijan. (2019, May 29). European Court of Human Rights. HUDOC – European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 15172/13. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-193543>
21. Jahn, J. (2014). Ruling (in)directly through individual measures? Effect and legitimacy of the ECtHR's new remedial power. *ZaöRV*, 74, 1–39. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from https://www.zaoerv.de/74_2014/74_2014_1_a_1_40.pdf
22. Jella and Others v. Albania. (2024, March 5). European Court of Human Rights. HUDOC – European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 7564/07. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-231333>
23. Luli and Others v. Albania. (2014, April 1). European Court of Human Rights, Applications nos. 64480/09, 64482/09, 12874/10, 56935/10, 3129/12 and 31355/09. HUDOC - European Court of Human Rights. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-142305>
24. Papamichalopoulos and Others v. Greece (Article 50). (1995, October 31). European Court of Human Rights. HUDOC – European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 14556/89. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-57961>
25. Parliamentary Assembly. (1998, October 21). Constitution of the Republic of Albania, Adopted by Law no. 8417, dated 21.10.1998. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://euralius.eu/index.php/en/library/albanian-legislation?task=download.send&id=178&catid=9&mid=0>
26. Ramadhi and Others v. Albania. (2007, November 13). European Court of Human Rights. HUDOC – European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 38222/02. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-83249>
27. Stone Sweet, A. (2012). A cosmopolitan legal order: Constitutional pluralism and rights adjudication in Europe. *Journal of Global Constitutionalism*, 1(1), 53–90. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1913657>
28. Supreme Court of Albania. (2012, March 7). Decision no. 01226/2011.
29. Supreme Court of Albania. (2021, July 22). Decision no. 00-2021-1317.
30. Suso Musa v. Malta. (2013, July 23). European Court of Human Rights. HUDOC – European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 42337/12. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-122893>
31. Xheraj v. Albania. (2008, July 29). European Court of Human Rights, Application no. 37959/02. HUDOC - European Court of Human Rights. Retrieved January 30, 2026, from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-87964>